

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract

The article discusses ways to develop the professional communicative competence of future teachers of foreign languages. This process aims to provide students with professional communicative knowledge, promote values that go beyond motivation, and build useful abilities for intercultural and professional language communication. The introduction of the article explains the relevance and importance of the formation of professional communicative competence in accordance with the requirements of modern society.

Keywords: professional communicative competence, foreign language education, English in high educational institutions, foreign language teachers, active learning methods.

The challenge of developing a professionally competent worker in every area of contemporary production has lately been particularly pertinent in foreign scientists' psychological and pedagogical studies, independence, discipline, communication, and the urge for self-development are prioritized as parts of the spectrum of personal psychological qualities in the "competent worker" paradigm created by American social science, which is receiving significant attention in the workforce. The ability to autonomously solve complicated issues, the possession of fresh information, skills, and capacities, a good self-image, the ability for pleasant communication, and teamwork are only a few characteristics emphasized in Western European conceptions of competence.

The development of creative capabilities has replaced the highly specialized (functional) training of professionals as the primary objective that takes precedence over all others at academic institutions in the USA. Competence (knowledge of the most productive way to work that requires the least amount of time) is one of the numerous factors used to evaluate an American leader's corporate culture [1]. The addition of a foreign language required a change in the focus placed on teacher development. As a result, one of the top concerns of a pedagogical university is the development of communicative skills in prospective foreign language instructors.

The term "competence" has just lately gained popularity in the literature on psychology, education, and methodology. Thus, a competency-based approach to education is emerging in the late 1960s to early 1970s in western literature, and in the late 1980s in domestic literature. The concept of "competence" was not defined in detail throughout that time of methodological science development [2]. Numerous scientists have presented their theories about this matter. Professionalism's key component and a sign of its high caliber is "professional competence." The successful resolution of professional issues in a particular direction, which underlie different categories of competence, is how professional competence is articulated. The assignment

of professionalism to the average directions of development of a specialist determines the following types of professional competence: special, social, and personal. Special or service professional competence is defined as the ability to perform a service at a high professional level and the possession of both special knowledge and the practical application of that knowledge.

Social professional competence is characterized by the use of professional communication strategies recognized in the professional community, strategies for joint professional action, and partnership. Individual professional competence is characterized by skillful ways of self-expression and self-development. Having considered professional competencies, G.A. Larinova called the center competence "intercultural and sectoral information, aptitudes, and opportunities essential for effective work in different professional communities" [3].

The ability of a person (O. I. Matyash, N. A. Moreva, N. D. Galskova, N. I. Gez, I. A. Zimnyaya, etc.); possession of skills and abilities (V. B. Kashkin, G. O. Chanysheva, etc.); willingness and ability to communicate are the current definitions of communicative competence (I. L. Bim, D. A. Ivanov, etc.). We believe it is important to concentrate on the concept of "readiness" because, in our study, we are discussing the professional preparation of aspiring teachers, which has as its goal readiness for pedagogical activity. When we summarize the various perspectives on the preparedness issue, we can identify two major methods for studying it:

1. The study of readiness as a complex personal formation, a diverse and layered structure of traits, properties, and states that collectively enable a given subject to perform actions with varying degrees of success (K. M. Durai-Novakova, M. I. Dyachenko, L. A. Kandybovich, V. A. Slastenin, and others).

2. The study of readiness as a particular functional state, as a psychological requirement for an activity's success, as a selective activity that shapes the body and personality for the upcoming activity; as a psychological attitude that operates in opposition to the

organism's overall activity, as a state preceding behavior; as socially fixed attitudes that define a person's social behavior (P. P. Gornostai, L. V. Kondrashova, etc.) [4].

The concepts and content of this procedure are the content component of the process of developing the professional communicative ability of prospective foreign language teachers. Future foreign language teachers' professional communicative competence is developed in accordance with a set of overarching pedagogical principles.

We add the following to the principles of professional communicative competence development for future foreign language teachers:

1. Cooperation across disciplines (integration). Interdisciplinary coordination is defined as the consolidation of the scientific content of the various academic specialties. Researchers (N. Chebyshev, V. Kagan) assert that the fundamental idea of interdisciplinary integration is that every cognitive and professional problem is always multidisciplinary, necessitates analysis and resolution from the perspective of related disciplines, and subsequently unifies disciplinary decisions into a comprehensive picture. According to V. Idiatulin, the idea of knowledge consolidation is also contemporary in terms of general cultural trends, such as the desire for a unified systematic picture of the world, overcoming a limited perspective of the world, and the blending of cultures. When the disciplines share a topic, it is obviously possible. Interdisciplinary coordination should be understood as the capacity to apply the methods, core ideas, and tools used by academic disciplines, as well as the learned abilities, to address challenges in the areas of cognition, education, and the workplace [5].

2. The premise of a personality-oriented attitude to education is parity in instructional contact. This idea is founded on the mutual conditionality and different dynamic interconnections of all elements of the educational process, as well as the equitable interaction of all participants in the educational process. Relationships between "teacher" and "student" are based on the partnership-based principles of shared activities and cooperation with a common purpose. The student and the teacher were considered equal subjects. Students actively participate in the selection, organization, and design of the content of a particular lesson. The student is the subject of the educational process, with a unique view of the world, needs and motivations, and sociocultural and individual development programs. The instructor serves as an adviser, assistant, and participant in the classes. The study group as a whole, the teacher, and each individual student should all be equally prioritized throughout the educational process.

3. The idea of student consciousness and engagement in learning, with the teacher taking the lead. The integration of teaching and learning is natural for the learning process. The holistic learning process only produces the desired outcome when these two processes work together. If the teacher actively instructs and the student does not take part in the process of gaining knowledge, skills, and abilities, success is hard to predict. Furthermore, it is well recognized that learning advances more rapidly when it is expertly handled by

the teacher, whether directly or indirectly. This idea highlights the active role that students play in their training and emphasizes that they are the learning's topic, not its passive object. Students' activities should focus more on the process of self-acquisition of knowledge than on memorization and attention, when the student explores the facts and provides conclusions and generalizations, concretizes his knowledge, finds and fixes errors and inaccuracies, and develops a plan for new learning activities. Conditions are created for getting fantastic results in a shorter period of time when the teacher's and the student's activities combine. Teaching must be both conscious and active [6].

These principles determine the nature and content of the activities of the teacher and students in the process of developing the professional communicative competence of future teachers of a foreign language.

As we can see, different authors identify a different number of communicative competence components and provide different terminology for their nomination, characterizing the component composition as a complicated scientific concept. We present the framework of professional communicative competence of a future foreign language teacher after analyzing the generalized provisions of approaches to the definition and structure of communicative competence and relying on the contemporary goal of teaching a foreign language (preparation for genuine intercultural communication). a cognitive component Professional communication expertise will be the primary component of this component. The knowledge data structure consists of the following elements:

1. linguistic (knowledge about the system of the language being studied; acquaintance with the structure, meaning, and morphological and syntactic behavior of lexical items in both oral and written forms; acquaintance with the settings in which they are typically used);

2. intercultural (knowledge of other groups or cultures, characteristics of social interaction in professional contexts of a different speech community, knowledge of the semantics and relationships of words, and concepts; knowledge of the common and distinctive characteristics of cultures, ways of their linguistic and nonlinguistic expression);

3. socio-psychological (understanding of the psychological basis of professional communication: means and methods of interaction, the laws of forming interpersonal interactions, as well as communication technology). As the previous analysis of communicative competence demonstrates, nearly all researchers stress that its nature is shown in the practical activity of a person in the execution of the abilities of helpful, constructive interpersonal and intercultural communication.

All this gives grounds to single out a practical component in the structure of professional communicative competence of future foreign language teachers. This component includes a set of professional communication skills:

- 1) the ability to freely use linguistic knowledge in the process of communication to adequately express information;

2) the ability to relate to the internal state, the development of self-determination of a person from another cultural group, the ability to perceive someone else's and build one's speech within the framework of the culture of the country of the studied and native languages in various situations communication;

3) the ability to influence the individual and the team, to control one's behavior, which means mastery of one's body (facial expressions, pantomimic), emotions, and mood.

The value-motivational component is one of the crucial elements of professional communication skills. A person's wants, desires, and interests are characterized by their motivation, which is a collection of psychological factors that explain human behavior. Values serve as a guide in reality, are reflected in a person's mind as value orientations, are part of the individual's psychological make-up, and provide motivation for her behavior. Values are defined in philosophy as "specifically social definitions of objects of the surrounding world, revealing their positive or negative value for a person and society" [7]. National and universal values influence how people behave, allow you to assess your own conduct in relation to that of others and other people's behavior, and let you select your preferred method of communication. This element is determined by the student's system of motivations, values, and meanings regarding comprehension and proper application, independent search for knowledge gaps, independent application of the known methods of action to unfamiliar, atypical situations, a manifestation of thought activity, initiative, and independence in action assessment. Along with the development of tolerance for other nations, peoples, cultures, and social groupings, the component also entails the building of students' social attitudes and value-oriented predispositions for intercultural conversation and exchange. Since students construct their own lines of behavior, these elements have a strong personal value for them and are the primary indicator of a high degree of development of professional communication ability (in this case, in relation to the process of mastering a foreign language).

Conversations, discussions, story times, conferences, festivals, meetings with foreign language teachers, independent student research projects, and other

forms of pedagogical process organization are used to develop the professional communicative competence of future foreign language teachers. These methods help to develop the unity of the cognitive, practical, and value-motivational components of professional communicative competence. Determining the effectiveness of the ongoing pedagogical process, that is, the degree to which the results obtained with the goals set, analyzing the reasons for the appearance of negative results of pedagogical interaction, identifying ways to correct the shortcomings of the pedagogical activity, and making the necessary adjustments are all part of the evaluative and effective component of the development of professional communicative competence of future teachers of a foreign language. As a result, the interaction between the highlighted elements of prospective foreign language teachers' professional communicative competence development supports the validity of the ongoing educational process.

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